

A New Method to Purify Hapten-Protein Conjugate

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Manuscript received 26 March 1996, revised 30 October 1996, accepted 7 March 1997

The specific binding proteins used in immunoassays are the antibodies elicited by active immunisation with the substances to be measured in biological fluids. Substances with molecular weight (less than 1000) are essentially nonimmunogenic¹. To produce antibodies against these substances they must be covalently coupled to large molecules like serum albumin (bovine or human), thyroglobulin or hemocyanin etc. The covalent linkage is most commonly a peptide bond where the carboxyl function on the steroid is coupled to amino groups of lysine residues on albumin. During the past two decades using the hapten-protein conjugates, antisera to practically all the hormones and drugs have been generated and immunoassays developed to estimate the particular compound in biological fluids.

During the course of work on steroid immunoassays in our laboratory over the past several years, it has been observed that the molar ratio of the steroid on protein is very important to get consistent immune response in terms of titer of antisera obtained. If the mass of the steroid on albumin is below 6000, or the molar ratio is below 20 for a steroid of molecular weight 300, the immune response is unpredictable. If the mass exceeds 12000 or the molar ratio is around 35–40 then the conjugate tends to become water-insoluble. However, if the mass is about 8000–9000 or the molar ratio is between 26–30, the immune response in terms of antibody production is consistent and in some cases very high titer antiserum is produced. In other words, it is extremely important to define the exact molar ratio of the steroid-protein conjugate, making sure that during the estimation there is no contribution from uncoupled hapten as it will give incorrect molar incorporation thus rendering it either poorly immunogenic or nonimmunogenic. There is no definite data reported in the literature defining the exact molar ratio to achieve a good titer and consistent immune response in all the animals used for immunisation. The methods used commonly for calculation of molar ratio is either by uv spectrometry² or by incorporation of radiolabeled hapten³ during conjugation.

In the present study we report the use of silica gel as a new and inexpensive matrix for the purification of steroid-protein conjugate for calculation of molar incorporation. By this method almost complete separation between un-

coupled hapten and conjugate was achieved. Using such conjugates it was observed that all the rabbits used for immunisation gave consistent response in terms of antibody production.

Results and Discussion

After initial step of dialysis of the hapten-protein conjugate to remove the uncoupled hapten, methods that have been used to separate uncoupled hapten are gel filtration on sephadex or sepharose⁴ column. These methods have been proved unsatisfactory as all the hapten entrapped in the crevices of the protein can not be removed. In our laboratory at least two or three subsequent purification of the conjugate on sephadex had to be done till there was no change in the molar ratio of the conjugate. We used this molar ratio to determine whether a particular conjugate could be used for antibody production or not.

We observed that silica gel with mesh size 200–400 is very cheap and convenient to purify the hapten-protein conjugate for the purpose of molar ratio determination and subsequent use to produce antisera. Using this method almost complete separation between uncoupled hapten and conjugate was achieved. This was in contrast to the purification on sephadex G-25 where at least two successive purification were required to get consistent results and is in agreement to the earlier reports on the discrepancy in purification of hapten-protein conjugate on sephadex or sepharose^{3,4}. Moreover, sephadex and sepharose are comparatively costly chemicals.

Molar ratios of steroid-protein conjugates are presented in Table 1. Characteristics of steroid antisera generated from purified conjugates are given in Table 2 and the data on specificity of steroid antiserum in Table 3.

TABLE I

Steroid-protein conjugate	Molar ratio
Estradiol-6-(<i>O</i> -carboxymethyl)oxime-BSA (1)	27
Testosterone-3-(<i>O</i> -carboxymethyl)oxime-BSA (2)	31
Progesterone-11 α -hemisuccinate-BSA (3)	32
Cortisol-3-(<i>O</i> -carboxymethyl)oxime-BSA (4)	25

The data generated in our laboratory on purified conjugate of well defined molar ratio indicated that the conjugates of molar ratio of more than 35 became water-in-

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CDRI Communication # 5166.

TABLE 2—CHARACTERISTICS OF STEROID ANTISERA GENERATED FROM PURIFIED CONJUGATES

Steroid antisera	Titer	Sensitivity pg/tube	Standard curve range pg	50% Intercept pg
Estradiol	1 : 900000	6.25	6.25–200	35–40
Testosterone	1 : 400000	12.5	12.5–400	65–70
Progesterone	1 : 15000	12.5	12.5–400	80–100

TABLE 3—SPECIFICITY OF STEROID ANTISERUM

Antiserum	Cross reacting steroids	% Cross reaction
Estradiol	Estradiol	100
	Estriol	0.41
	Estrone	1.86
	Cortisol	>0.005
Progesterone	Progesterone	100
	Cortisol	>0.05
	Testosterone	>0.05
	17-Hydroxyprogesterone	0.91
	20 α -Hydroxyprogesterone	0.28
Testosterone	Testosterone	100
	5 α -Dihydrotestosterone	36.92
	Androstenedione	0.28
	Androstenediol	2.05
	Androsendiol	0.08

soluble. With the conjugates of molar ratio of less than 20, all the rabbits did not responded with antibody production and those who responded with antibody production the titers were very low. Similar views were expressed in the published literature⁵ where conjugates having molar ratio of less than 20 (determined without purification of conjugate) gave no antibody response or the titer remained low and the antisera could not be used for assay development.

Conjugates characterised by the present method and having molar ratio 26–30 or mass of steroid 8000–9000 on protein gave consistent immune response in terms of titer in all the rabbits used for immunisation. A very important

observation has been made that by using these purified and well characterised conjugates of progesterone, testosterone and estradiol, very high titer antibodies in the range of 1 : 150000 to 1 : 900000 as final dilution in assay system were produced in rabbits (Table 1). To the best of our knowledge it is first time polyclonal antisera of such high titer in rabbits is reported. This work to some extent gives answers to the myth that the antibody production is like black magic.

Experimental

The steroids, BSA, Freund's complete adjuvant (all Sigma), carboxymethylamine hemihydrochloride, succinic anhydride, tri-*n*-butylamine, isobutyl chlorocarbonate (all Aldrich), tritiated steroids (Amarsham International) and silica gel (mesh 200–400; E. Merck) were used.

Preparation of steroid-protein conjugate : The steroid derivatives estradiol-6-(*O*-carboxymethyl)oxime, testosterone-3-(*O*-carboxymethyl)oxime, progesterone-11 α -hemisuccinate and cortisol-3-(*O*-carboxymethyl)oxime were synthesised by known methods⁶. Steroid-protein conjugates such as estradiol-6-(*O*-carboxymethyl)oxime-BSA (1), testosterone-3-(*O*-carboxymethyl)oxime-BSA (2), progesterone-11 α -hemisuccinate-BSA (3) and cortisol-3-(*O*-carboxymethyl)oxime-BSA (4) were prepared by mixed anhydride² method with some modification.

Estradiol-6(*O*-carboxymethyl)oxime-bovine serum albumin : To a solution of estradiol-6-(*O*-carboxymethyl)oxime (0.099 g, 0.277 mmol) in dry dioxane (3 ml) was added tri-*n*-butylamine and the solution was cooled to 10°. Isobutyl chloroformate (0.04 ml, 0.28 mmol) was added under stirring and the reaction was proceeded for further 20 min at 10°. The reaction mixture was then added in one portion to a well-stirred and cooled (4°) solution of bovine serum albumin (0.5 g, 0.007 mmol) prepared in a mixture of water-dioxane (60 : 40, w/v) and 1 *N* NaOH solution (0.5 ml). Stirring and cooling continued for 4 h and pH of the reaction mixture was maintained at 8.8–9.0 by adding 0.1 *N* NaOH solution. After completion of reaction, the conjugate was dialysed for 72 h against frequent changes of distilled water.

Purification procedure : Steroid-protein conjugate (approximately 1 mg in 0.1–0.2 ml water) obtained after dialysis was applied to silica gel column (0.5 cm \times 5 cm; silica gel packed suspended in triple-distilled water and equilibrated with distilled triple-distilled water). The fractions were eluted with triple-distilled water at a flow rate of 4–5 ml⁻¹ h. Fraction collected immediately after void volume was evaluated for the presence of conjugate. Upto 80% of protein was recovered in the fraction obtained after void volume. The remaining protein eluted in next two-three fractions. Molar ratio determined by uv spectrometry after purification of different conjugates on silica gel

column are given in Table 1.

Production of antisera : Antisera against three steroids 1-3 were raised in white New Zealand and/or Belgian rabbits by intradermal multisite injections⁷. Approximately 0.5 mg of conjugate emulsified with Freund's complete adjuvant (FCA) was used for immunisation (equivalent to 80 µg of steroid residue) on 50 to 60 sites. Intramuscular boosters were given 45 days after the initial immunisation and thereafter every 30 days, bleedings collected 15 days after every booster, and serum was separated and stored at -20° till analysed.

Radioimmunoassay procedure : Radioimmunoassay was performed⁸ using tritiated steroids. In a glass tube (12 mm dia × 55 mm length), steroid standards (made in 0.1 molar phosphate buffer containing 0.1% gelatin, pH 7.2-7.4; 0.5 ml), appropriately diluted antisera (0.1 ml) and tritiated steroid (10000 dpm) (0.1 ml) were incubated overnight at 4°. The following day dextran coated charcoal (0.625% charcoal solution containing 10% dextran; 0.2 ml) and after 15 min, the tubes were centrifuged at 750 g for 10 min at 4°. The supernatant was decanted in counting vials and counts were measured for a minimum of 2 min. Antisera characteristics (Table 2) like sensitivity and specificity were comparable to that reported in literature⁶ and with antisera supplied by WHO⁸.

Acknowledgement

The authors wish to thank Dr. V. P. Kamboj, Director, C.D.R.I., Lucknow, for encouragement. This work was supported by a task force grant from I.C.M.R., New Delhi. One of the authors (A.K.S.) thanks I.C.M.R., New Delhi, for financial support.

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